

ADDRESSING EFFICIENCY AND SECURITY ISSUES THROUGH ORACLE

PROJECT STATUS INQUIRY (PSI) AUTOMATION

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Abstract: As a temporary endeavor, every project is aimed to develop a distinctive product or service with a well defined beginning and end, often constrained by funding and deliverables, to meet specific goals and objectives, typically bringing value additions. Planning, coordinating and controlling the efforts of the personnel, as such, is a pre-requisite of every project management system. This leads to optimization of resources, bringing efficiency in the overall working of any enterprise. The work breakdown structure, at the base of any project management system, tends to create synergy, reducing transaction cost and time. Efficient management of resources is the slogan of modern management. Automation of operations, including system generated mailing systems on timely basis, are the hallmarks of enhancing procedures and proper management of time and resources.

Key words: Project management, Work breakdown structure, Oracle E-Business suite

1. Preface

The objective of this paper is to provide an insight about the effective management of resources and time at FCI, through a well planned and executed project management system.

The paper has been organized as per the following structure below:

1. Introduction
2. Oracle EBS
3. Impediments
4. Process of automation
5. Conclusion
6. References

2. Introduction

Project management is the systematic planning, organizing, motivating and controlling resources to achieve desired requirements. A project, by definition, is a temporary endeavor, aimed at developing a unique product or service with a defined beginning and end, in order to meet specific goals and objective. Being temporary in nature, a project has well defined beginning and end. This essential feature of any project puts up constraints on its scope and resources. A project is unique, different from the routine operations, but a specific set of operations to meet a specific singular goal. The distinction between Project management and the project seems to be less than precise. However a better appreciation of the distinction between the two can bring higher possibility of project success (Munns and Bjeirmi 1996). The success of a project depends on

how the owner, contractor and consultant have the idea about what success is. If they have different ideas about success, then possibly no one will be satisfied with the completion of the project (Hartman and Ashrafi 2002). Furthermore, identification and quantification and management of risks associated with information technology projects is an essential requirement for their successful delivery. The ignorance on part of an effective risk management has been the main reason for the high failure rate of information technology projects (Baccarini, Salm and Love 2004). The implementation of Standardized Project Management (SPM), defined as a standardized set of project management policies, lead to improvement of project performance. However, companies need to standardize project management practices only to a certain extent (Milosevic and Patanakul 2005).

Traditionally, every project management system is based on the accomplishment of a sequence of steps. The various developmental components of a project are:

1. Initiation
2. Planning and Design
3. Executing
4. Monitoring and Control
5. Closing

Every project management system has an initiation stage, followed by iterations of the following three stages, i.e., planning and design, executing, and monitoring and control, and finally termination of the project after the requirement is achieved (Figure 1).

Figure 1

Project management aims at answering three basic and necessary questions regarding the efficiency of operations. Whenever there are some deviations from the plans already established, inconsistent to the specific requirements of the project, necessary corrective action is taken to keep the resources on the right track (Figure 2).

Figure 2

The history of project management goes back to the development of Program Evaluation Review Technique (PERT) and Critical Path Mechanism (CPM), first of all applied to operations management. Project management is based on the Work Breakdown System (WBS). WBS involves project network modeling in which the entire job is subdivided into manageable work tasks. It shows the relation between the whole and the desired end result, as well as the

relationship between an individual task and all the other tasks. It involves allocation of responsibility with the identification of resources required and time available, at each stage of project monitoring and management. A simple version of WBS has been shown below (Figure 3).

Figure 3

The knowledge built or the technology development projects are the foundation for new product or new process. These are vital for the prosperity of the modern enterprise. But these typical projects are often mismanaged due to application of inappropriate financial criteria for project selection or wrong processes to manage them (Cooper 2007). There have been evidences in literature regarding the factors responsible for the success of a project. Personnel factors, based on correlation analysis, do not show a significant impact on project success. Human resource management is still found to be very rudimental in project context. However, there should be an improvement in the construct validity of the personnel variable. For the three distinct structures (functional, project-based and matrix), management support and trouble-shooting variables have been found to be significantly correlated with project success (Belout and Gauvreau 2004).

3. Oracle EBS

Oracle E-Business Suite (EBS), similar to any ERP products, is an internet enabled product that can be managed from a single site. The applications in Oracle EBS include:

- Oracle CRM
- Oracle Financials
- Oracle HRMS
- Oracle Logistics
- Oracle Supply Chain Applications
- Oracle Order Management
- Oracle Transportation Management
- Oracle Warehouse Management System

Oracle EBS provides a project module which enables for a better project management process. For every project, the constraints like funding, expenditure, costing, revenue and many other factors are pivotal for its successful implementation and execution. Oracle EBS provides a work breakdown structure (WBS), assigning the various tasks to the required personnel at different hierarchical levels. This leads to the optimization of resources and brings efficiency in project execution. Oracle EBS has thus been able to create harmony among the various sub tasks. Besides establishing a proper division of tasks, it provides budget details including costing, billing, expenditure, revenue and funding details.

The Oracle EBS has an inbuilt security mechanism that stops leakage of critical information to the unauthorized personnel. It provides a project status inquiry (PSI) window, which is

accessible to the key members (including project manager, offshore manager, task approver manager, etc). The Oracle EBS allows the key members to login with their secure credentials, in order to view and update the projects. The managers, who have the special access to PSI, monitor the projects on a continuous basis regarding the cost, budget, revenue, expenditure details. This provides for a regular up gradation of the various sub-tasks for a better control mechanism.

4. Impediments

Oracle EBS has been enabling the enterprise to successfully accomplish the projects well in time. Time for any organization is a scarce commodity. However there are various hurdles which hinder the time efficiency. This leads to suboptimal results, which hamper the corporate goal in the present day highly competitive markets.

First of all, the process of updating the actual tab from PAS to an excel spreadsheet with the built-in Project Financial Tracking Tool (PFTT) of the Oracle EBS provides a manual interface. This consumes a lot of time in extracting the financial details of each project one by one. Another issue that arises relates to the security issue of government organizations. The firewalls for security reasons disables the PMs and DMs working on government sites to have access to the Oracle EBS. This makes it difficult for the onsite managers to get the full details of their projects.

In order to overcome the issues mentioned above and at the same time maintaining confidentiality issues of the government sites, the above process was automated in such a way that the PM's and DM's receive the financial data of their respective projects through a system generated email on a weekly basis.

5. Process of automation

In order to manage time and resources efficiently, leading to optimal resource utilization, a program was scheduled on a weekly basis that mails the details of each project to the respective PM's or DM's. All the projects with their associated manager's emails were taken in a lookup and their respective flags were enabled. After running the program all the PM's or DM's would get the financial details of their respective projects on a weekly basis via a system generated email. This improved time efficiency and enabled the management to focus more on monitoring and control. Apart from this, managers working on site for government organizations could also receive the financial data of their respective projects without causing any breach of security.

The data template was designed to be bilingual, i.e., both English and French, so as to meet the requirements of those managers who knew only French. Also, the program was coded in such a way that it can send the financial data of a particular project to more than one manager if such need arises.

However, if a project gets closed, a mail is automatically sent to its respective manager with additional information, that, the project is closed on PAS. Thus, in the next weekly run, the flag of a closed project gets automatically disabled and it's no longer included for further mailing of details to its PM or DM.

This is a very positive step towards providing the delivery and the finance teams with timely PAS information to assist with more timely and accurate forecasting, proper revenue recognition, cost control leading to margin improvement, and overall an efficient financial management of projects.

6. Conclusion

The oracle EBS has been a revolutionary step towards successful project completions, enabling access to project details, and helping to monitor and control the financial aspects of the projects. However, due to the manual extraction of PAS details, often time consuming, and the inability of the onsite PM's or DM's to have access to Oracle EBS of government organizations, the overall organizational goal of optimization of resources was defeated. Automation of this process has led to an efficient financial management of the projects. The management will now be able to give more time to important and crucial issues like monitoring and control. Overall, this is a very positive step towards a better management of time and resources.

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